

Appendix A

Key	Authors	Title
S005	Susana Bautista; Raquel Hervás; Agustín Hernández-Gil; Carlos Martínez-Díaz; Sergio Pascua; Pablo Gervás	Aratraductor: text to pictogram translation using natural language processing techniques
S007	Rodrigo Alarcon; Lourdes Alarcon; Lourdes Moreno; Paloma Ana B Martínez	Word-Sense disambiguation system for text readability
S009	Francesco Barbieri; Germán Kruszewski; Francesco Ronzano; Horacio Saggion	How Cosmopolitan Are Emojis?: Exploring Emojis Usage and Meaning over Different Languages with Distributional Semantics
S012	Toshiki Tomihira; Atsushi Otsuka; Akihiro Yamashita; Tetsuji Satoh	What Does Your Tweet Emotion Mean?: Neural Emoji Prediction for Sentiment Analysis
S014	Nanxuan Zhao; Namwook Kim; Laura Mariah Herman; Hanspeter Pfister; Rynson Lau; Jose I Echevarria; Zoya Bylinskii	ICONATE: Automatic Compound Icon Generation and Ideation
S019	Horacio Saggion; Daniel Ferrés; Leen Sevens; Ineke Schuurman; Marta Ripollés; Olga Rodríguez	Able to Read My Mail: An Accessible e-Mail Client with Assistive Technology
S033	Akshi Kumar; Saurabh Raj Sangwan; Adarsh Kumar Singh; Gandharv Wadhwa	Hybrid Deep Learning Model for Sarcasm Detection in Indian Indigenous Language Using Word-Emoji Embeddings
S037	Kazunari Ito	Pictogramming — programming learning environment using human pictograms
S039	Hasan Fleyeh; Mark Dougherty; Dinesh Aenugula; Sruthi Baddam	Invariant Road Sign Recognition with Fuzzy ARTMAP and Zernike Moments
S041	Da Li; Rafal Rzepka; Michal Ptaszynski; Kenji Araki	Emoticon-Aware Recurrent Neural Network Model for Chinese Sentiment Analysis
S063	Cabello Laura; Lleida Eduardo; Simón Javier; Miguel Antonio Ortega	Text-to-pictogram summarization for augmentative and alternative communication
S065	Andrei Mikheev	Text Segmentation
S066	Naotsune Hosono; Hiromitsu Inoue; Hiroyuki Miki; Michio Suzuki; Yuji Nagashima; Yutaka Tomita; Sakae Yamamoto	Service Science Method to Create Pictograms Referring to Sign Languages
S067	Chuchu Liu; Xu Tan; Tao Zhou; Wei Zhang; Jianguo Liu; Xin Lu	Emoji use in China: popularity patterns and changes due to COVID-19
S076	Kenichi Horie; Yoshiharu Maeno; Yukio Ohsawa	Human-interactive annealing process with pictogram for extracting new scenarios for patent technology
S079	Atif Muhammadiyah; Franconi Valentina	Tell Me More: Automating Emojis Classification for Better Accessibility and Emotional Context Recognition
S081	Norré, Magali; Vandeghinste, Vincent; Bouillon, Pierrette; François, Thomas	Extending a Text-to-Pictograph System to French and to Arasaac
S083	Hervás, Raquela; Bautista, Susana; Méndez, Gonzalo; Galván, Paloma; Gervás, Pablo	Predictive composition of pictogram messages for users with autism

S081	Norré, Magali; Vandeghinste, Vincent; Bouillon, Pierrette; François, Thomas	Extending a Text-to-Pictograph System to French and to Arasaac
S083	Hervás, Raquela; Bautista, Susana; Méndez, Gonzalo; Galván, Paloma; Gervás, Pablo	Predictive composition of pictogram messages for users with autism
S086	Vandeghinste, Vincent; Sevens Ineke Schuurman Leen; Van Eynde Frank	Translating text into pictographs
S090	Perri Seneca; Argo Lauren; Kuang Jinju; Bui Duy; Hill Brent; Bray Bruce; Treitler-Zeng Qing	A picture's meaning: The design and evaluation of pictographs illustrating patient discharge instructions
S095	Mihalcea Rada; Leong Chee Wee	Toward communicating simple sentences using pictorial representations
S101	Simon Fong	Measuring emotions from online news and evaluating public models from netizens' comments: A text mining approach
S102	Flávio Arthur Oliveira Santos; Carlos Augusto E M Júnior; Hendrik Teixeira Macedo; Marco T Chella	CA2JU: An Assistive Tool for Children with Cerebral Palsy
S110	Bernard Jürgen; Hutter Marco; Sedlmair Michael; Zeppelzauer Matthias; Munzner Tamara	A Taxonomy of Property Measures to Unify Active Learning and Human-centered Approaches to Data Labeling
S126	Neamtu Rodica; André Camara; Carlos Pereira; Rafael Ferreira	Using Artificial Intelligence for Augmentative Alternative Communication for Children with Disabilities
S131	Dong Chuanhai; Jiajun Zhang; Chengqing Zong; Masanori Hattori; Hui Di	Character-Based LSTM-CRF with Radical-Level Features for Chinese Named Entity Recognition
S133	Lundälv Mats; Sandra Derbring	AAC Vocabulary Standardisation and Harmonisation
S148	Bocklet Tobias; Andreas Maier; Elmar Nöth	Age Determination of Children in Preschool and Primary School Age with GMM-Based Supervectors and Support Vector Machines/Regression
S154	Mihalcea Rada; Chee Wee Leong	Toward communicating simple sentences using pictorial
S171	Pereira Jayr; Natália Franco; Robson Fidalgo	A Semantic Grammar for Augmentative and Alternative Communication Systems
S189	Peng Haiyun; Yukun Ma; Soujanya Poria; Yang Li; Erik Cambria	Phonetic-enriched text representation for Chinese sentiment analysis with reinforcement learning
S190	Li Da; Rafal Rzepka; Michal Ptaszynski; Kenji Araki	HEMOS: A novel deep learning-based fine-grained humor detecting method for sentiment analysis of social media
S195	Peng Haiyun; Yukun Ma; Yang Li; Erik Cambria	Learning multi-grained aspect target sequence for Chinese sentiment analysis
S199	Urabe Yuki; Rafal Rzepka; Kenji Araki	Find right countenance for your input Improving automatic emoticon recommendation system with distributed representations
S200	García-Méndez Silvia; Milagros Fernández-Cavilanes; Enrique Costa-Montenegro; Jonathan Juncal-Martínez; F. Javier González-Castaño	A library for automatic natural language generation of spanish texts
S202	Pereira Jayr Alencar; David Macêdo; Cleber Zanchettin; Adriano Lorena Inácio de Oliveira; Robson do Nascimento Fidalgo.	PictoBERT: Transformers for next pictogram prediction
S203	Wolk Krzysztof; Agnieszka Wolk; Krzysztof Marasek; Wojciech Glinkowski	Pictogram-based mobile first medical aid communicator
S207	Baldassarri Sandra; Javier Marco Rubio; Marta García Azpiroz; Eva Cerezo	AraBoard: A Multiplatform Alternative and Augmentative Communication Tool

S208	Yu Yongtao; Jonathan Li; Chenglu Wen; Haiyan Guan; Huan Luo; Cheng Wang	Bag-of-visual-phrases and hierarchical deep models for traffic sign detection and recognition in mobile laser scanning data
S210	Lamy Jean-Baptiste; Lina F. Soualmia	Formalization of the semantics of iconic languages: An ontology-based method and four semantic-powered applications
S215	Cholewa Nicola; Krzysztof Wolk; Robert Wolk	Precise eye-tracking technology in medical communicator prototype
S217	Ellahyani Ayoub; Mohamed El Ansari; Ilyas El Jaafari	Traffic sign detection and recognition based on random forests

Table 1. Selected scientific articles in the discussion section.

Footnote Keys	
1	S005, S007, S009, S012, S014, S019, S033, S039, S041, S063, S065, S066, S079, S081, S083, S086, S126, S131, S133, S148, S154, S189, S190, S195, S199, S202
2	S005, S007, S009, S012, S014, S019, S033, S037, S039, S041, S063, S067, S079, S081, S083, S086, S090, S095, S102, S126, S133, S148, S154, S171, S190, S202, S203, S208, S215, S217
3	S005, S012, S019, S033, S041, S066, S067, S076, S079, S081, S095, S101, S102, S126, S148, S171, S190, S195, S199, S200, S202, S203, S210, S215, S217
4	S005, S012, S019, S033, S041, S067, S079, S081, S095, S102, S126, S148, S171, S190, S202, S203, S215, S217
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12	S005, S007, S009, S012, S014, S019, S033, S039, S041, S079, S081, S083, S086, S090, S101, S102, S126, S131, S148, S189, S190, S195, S199, S200, S202, S215
13	S005, S007, S009, S012, S014, S019, S033, S039, S041, S079, S081, S083, S086, S090, S101, S102, S110, S126, S131, S148, S189, S190, S195, S199, S200, S202, S207, S208, S210, S215, S217